

TATTIE SCONES

- 500g [floury potatoes](#), such as Maris Pipers or King Edwards, peeled
- 25g [butter](#)
- 2 [spring onions](#), finely sliced
- 100g [self-raising flour](#)
- salt and freshly ground [black pepper](#)

Method

1. Cut the potatoes into chunks and cook in a pan of salted water until tender. Drain and allow to air dry for a minute or two.
2. Mash until lump free, stir in the butter and when it has melted, stir in the spring onions and flour. Season with salt and pepper, then leave the mash until it's cool enough to handle.
3. Put half of the mixture onto a floured board and roll it into a disc about 20–25cm in diameter.
4. Cut into quarters and, using a fish slice, transfer these to a dry frying pan set over a medium heat – the idea is to toast the scones rather than fry them. Cook for 3–4 minutes per side until golden, then remove and keep warm. Repeat with the remaining mixture.